

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Improving mental health and wellbeing

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for Improving mental health and wellbeing with and through education settings

[CotN_Mental_health_Report_3.pdf](#)

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Most mental health conditions start by adolescence, with half established by age 14 years. In 2022, 18% of children aged 7 to 16 years and 22% of young people aged 17 to 24 years had a probable mental health condition.**
- **Rates of diagnosis have increased. Diagnosed anxiety, depression, attention, and eating disorders doubled between 2003 and 2018. COVID-19 restrictions likely had an additional impact.**
- **In addition to the impact on children and their families, mental health conditions have a large economic cost and impact on public services.** National lifetime loss of earnings for children in England who experienced anxiety problems age 14 and also failed to achieve at least five GCSEs amounts to more than £850 million.
- **Prevention of mental health conditions in children and young people will have life-long benefits to individuals and society, including economic benefits.** Mental health is affected by social and economic factors. However, intervention research has typically focused on psychological therapies and interventions targeting individual behaviours, rather than the social determinants of mental health conditions.
- **National level focus:**
 - Creation of NHS information hubs that provide a guide to the mental health and wellbeing provisions available locally.
 - Routinely collect data in schools to inform targeted provision of evidence-based approaches
 - Tackle the upstream determinants of poor mental health - including early support for neurodivergent children.
 - Expand the mental health support offered through schools and educational settings and expand efforts to make young people feel safe and supported in school (build 'healthy mind environments')
- **Local level focus:**
 - Improving the mental health of children and young people should be a local priority for all agencies.
 - Young people should be involved in finding local solutions to the issue.

The Problem: There is a crisis in CYP's mental health in the UK

Our CYP need good mental health and wellbeing to develop and flourish. This presents our society with a profound and complex set of challenges that require immediate and collaborative action. We are still spending billions on expensive crisis support, and on the costs of failing to provide help early.

One in six children aged 6-16 were identified as having a probable mental health problem in

Seven in ten parents said they received no support whilst their child was on the waiting list for NHS mental health services

Three in ten schools in England have dedicated mental health teams

"As young people, we give our opinions and then don't know what happens. We want our opinions to be acted on and that we are not always seen as kids."

What you can do at a local level

- **Collect data at a local level** to inform evidence-based interventions to address local need.
- **Ensure children and young people are involved** to coproduce local interventions.
- **Develop partnerships across sectors to leverage in resources, expertise and support.** This may include mentorships, training, internships, workshops, provision of equipment and training programmes.
- **Move to prevention strategies and early intervention to provide support at the point of need.**
- **Consider what can be done to address the upstream causes of poor mental health, such as poverty and early support for neurodivergent children.**
- **Consider how the local environment can be used to support good mental health, e.g. through access to green space, play facilities for children of varying ages.**
- **Build on but tailor the kinds of approaches featured below.**

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
#BeeWell a wellbeing measurement and improvement framework for secondary schools in Greater Manchester	#BeeWell is an innovative programme that blends academic research and youth-led change to 'pivot the system' such that wellbeing is given parity with academic attainment. Over 85,000 young people surveyed to date. A coalition of over 130 local organisations working in partnership.	Participating schools routinely use #BeeWell data to inform their provision. Year 10 mental wellbeing data adopted as a key performance indicator in Greater Manchester Combined Authority Strategy. A social prescribing programme (#BeeWell Champions) was launched in 5 GM neighbourhoods, selected using #BeeWell data.
Age of Wonder: a longitudinal cohort study in Bradford	Age of Wonder is a continuation of the Born in Bradford (BiB) longitudinal birth cohort study that began back in 2007. From 2022, BiB have been expanding the cohort to include up to 30,000 young people, with the research team joining them on their journey through adolescence and into adulthood.	Working with young people and families to co-produce a pipeline of initiatives that focus on early intervention, community and psychosocial interventions, and public mental health approaches to prevent mental ill-health. These interventions will be evaluated to deepen our understanding of what works for whom and in what settings.
The OxWell Student Survey: A student survey produced by The Liverpool Education Department and the OxWell Study team at The University of Oxford	Liverpool has been able to develop a data first approach to the needs of the students across the city using the data from the OxWell study. Working with public sector partners (such as the ICB and third sector organisations) the findings focused the response to support new strategies to address loneliness, racism, and bullying.	In 2022, a citywide grant scheme was initiated to support schools to respond to the OxWell findings. Schools were able to consider their own data to prioritise the interventions that support the needs of their students, and resource was allocated to help implement the plans. Interventions included programmes to improve resilience, sleep hygiene and team building. Training has been delivered to schools to support them design and deliver school-based action plans focusing on the young person's voice.
Online Social anxiety Cognitive therapy for Adolescents (OSCA)	OSCA (Online Social anxiety Cognitive therapy for Adolescents) is an internet-delivered therapist-assisted cognitive therapy for adolescent SAD. OSCA is made up of self-study modules and exercises that young people complete in their own time.	An RCT of OSCA conducted with young people (aged 14-18 years) recruited from state schools in London and the Southeast found that 77% who received immediate access to OSCA recovered, compared to only 14% who were allocated to a waitlist control condition.

Example	Approach	Impact
<p>The Relational Toolkit and The Young Advisors' River of Change</p>	<p>The aim of the Relational Toolkit is to encourage a different way of looking at engagement. The Relational Toolkit facilitated a Board-to-Board development day with the Child Health and Well-being Network North East and North Cumbria's Executive Board and Youth Board (Young Advisors aged 11-16 years), followed by a series of workshops with the Young Advisors.</p>	<p>The Toolkit activities enabled the adults and young people on the two Boards to share their experiences and understandings of working together and to move towards repositioning children and young people as expert decision makers and agents of change in developing the health and wellbeing policies and practices that affect them and their peers. The Young Advisors took the recommendations from the Development Day and, through a series of workshops, developed their ideas for a Theory of Change on how professionals and policy makers should approach working with CYP.</p>
<p>Next Door but One: The impact of creative arts and theatre on young people's mental health</p>	<p>In 2023 Next Door but One delivered five projects which actively worked with 524 CYP and reaching a further 800 audience members of theatre performances. Further information can be found via: https://www.nextdoorbutone.co.uk</p>	<p>100% said it helped them feel connected to other people. • 92% said it made them feel more confident in themselves and in doing new things. 83% had never seen theatre in a local library before.</p>
<p>Online Support and Intervention (OSI) platform case study</p>	<p>The recent CoCAT trial, in over 30 health organisations in England and Northern Ireland, showed that CBT could be delivered in an efficient and accessible way by helping parents to help their children apply CBT strategies in their child's day to day lives through an online support platform (OSI) with brief therapist support</p>	<p>Child mental health services across England are now implementing OSI in ways that increase access to treatment for child anxiety problems. For example, South Tyneside and Sunderland NHS Foundation Trust have put in place nominated champions within each area of the service to support all the therapists trained in OSI to help them navigate this new technology. The champions also offer supervision on the suitability and delivery of OSI to support parents and carers of children aged 5 to 12 years.</p>